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Predicting Success in Introductory Computing Course using Senior High School Specialized and Applied Coursework Data

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Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to predict student success in an Introduction to Computing course using Senior High School (SHS) specialized and applied coursework data, with particular focus on graduates from the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Information and Communications Technology (TVL-ICT) track. **Methods:** A quantitative predictive modeling approach was employed using educational data mining techniques. A decision tree classifier was developed based on the academic records of 258 first-year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology students. The model utilized grades from three applied courses and two specialized courses as input features, with student performance (pass/fail) as the target variable. Model performance was evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation. **Findings:** The results revealed that the model achieved an accuracy of 84.5%, indicating strong predictive capability. Among the predictors, specialized coursework emerged as the most significant factor influencing student success, while applied coursework demonstrated a secondary yet meaningful contribution. **Novelty:** This study contributes to the limited body of research linking SHS TVL-ICT academic preparation directly to college-level computing success through predictive modeling. This research specifically isolates the predictive value of specialized and applied SHS coursework using a decision tree approach. The study introduces a data-driven framework for early identification of at-risk students **Keywords:** Predictive modelling; Senior high school; Computing; Coursework; Decision tree

1 Introduction

The implementation of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533) introduced a major transformation in the Philippine education system through the K-12 curriculum, with the Senior High School (SHS) program designed to prepare learners for higher education, employment, and lifelong learning^{(1), (2)}. Anchored in outcomes-based education, the SHS curriculum emphasizes the development of both foundational knowledge and specialized competencies aligned with students' chosen

career pathways⁽³⁾. Within this framework, the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track, particularly the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) strand, is intended to equip students with practical, industry-relevant skills in areas such as programming, networking, and computer systems servicing⁽⁴⁾.

Despite this intended workforce-oriented preparation, a growing number of TVL-ICT graduates pursue higher education in computing-related programs⁽⁵⁾. This shift exposes a critical issue: the extent to which SHS preparation, originally designed for employability, effectively supports academic success in college-level computing courses remains unclear. While prior studies have established that academic background influences higher education outcomes, they often treat SHS performance as a general indicator rather than examining the differential impact of specific coursework components^{(6), (7), (8)}. More importantly, existing studies predominantly rely on traditional statistical methods, which are limited in their ability to model complex, non-linear relationships and to generate actionable predictions for early intervention. As a result, there remains a lack of predictive, data-driven approaches that can identify at-risk students before academic difficulties become critical.

Furthermore, current literature provides limited critical insight into the relative contribution of applied versus specialized subjects within the TVL-ICT curriculum. This represents a significant gap, as these components are designed to develop distinct but complementary competencies, practical skills and domain-specific knowledge, that may differently influence student performance in foundational computing courses. Without a clear understanding of their predictive value, curriculum alignment between SHS and higher education remains insufficiently informed.

To address these limitations, this study adopts an educational data mining approach to develop a predictive model of student success in an Introduction to Computing course using SHS coursework data from TVL-ICT graduates. Unlike prior studies that rely primarily on descriptive or inferential statistics, this research employs a decision tree classifier to capture non-linear relationships and provide interpretable predictive insights. Specifically, the study: (1) develops a classification model to predict student pass/fail outcomes, (2) determines the relative importance of applied and specialized SHS subjects, and (3) evaluates model performance using classification metrics.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative predictive modeling design using an Educational Data Mining (EDM) approach (Figure 1). EDM focuses on extracting meaningful patterns and knowledge from educational datasets through the application of machine learning techniques⁽⁹⁾. The goal of this study is to develop a classification model capable of predicting student performance in introductory computing courses based on their prior academic records in the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood – Information and Communications Technology (TVL-ICT) track. The research process follows a structured EDM workflow, which includes: 1) data collection, 2) preliminary data preparation, 3) statistical analysis, 4) data preprocessing, 5) data mining implementation, and 6) evaluation of outcomes. This systematic approach ensures the reliability and reproducibility of the predictive modeling process⁽¹⁰⁾.

Fig 1. Educational Data Mining Process^{(10), (11)}

2.2 Dataset and Participants

This study utilized a structured dataset derived from institutional academic records of First-Year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) students enrolled in an Introduction to Computing course. The dataset consists of 258 student records collected across the academic years 2020, 2021, and 2023. Inclusion criteria were restricted to students who completed the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood – Information and Communications Technology (TVL-ICT) track in Senior High School (SHS), ensuring alignment between prior academic preparation and the target course. The dataset includes grades from three applied subjects and two specialized subjects, which served as input features, while student performance in the Introduction

to Computing course (pass/fail) was used as the target variable. The dataset was obtained from institutional records with appropriate permissions; however, due to privacy and ethical restrictions, it is not publicly accessible. All personally identifiable information was removed prior to analysis to ensure data confidentiality and compliance with data protection standards. Future studies may consider the use of anonymized open educational datasets to enhance reproducibility. Prior to modeling, the dataset underwent preprocessing, including data cleaning, handling of missing values, and normalization of grade formats. Missing values were minimal and addressed using mean imputation to preserve dataset size while maintaining statistical integrity. Feature scaling was not applied, as tree-based models are insensitive to feature magnitude.

2.3 Data Encoding

Categorical grade values were transformed into ordinal numerical representations to allow model processing. The encoding scheme used is as follows:

Table 1. Encoding Scheme

Outstanding (O)	90-100
Very Satisfactory (VS)	85-89
Satisfactory (S)	80-84
Fair (F)	75-79
Did Not Meet Expectations (DME)	Below 75

Table 1 presents the categorical encoding of numerical grade ranges used in the study, where student performance in SHS applied and specialized subjects is classified into five levels. The encoding facilitates consistent data preprocessing and enables effective input representation for the predictive modeling process. The target variable was encoded as: Pass = 1, Fail = 0, while grades of students were obtained from the following subjects: Applied Courses: AP1, AP2, AP3; Specialized Courses: SP1, SP2.

2.4 Predictive Model

The success of Educational Data Mining (EDM) Applications is largely dependent on the effective use of descriptive and predictive data mining models⁽¹²⁾. The selection of models for a particular problem is crucial in achieving the desired outcomes. This research will use the decision tree predictive model.

Decision tree model a decision tree algorithm that separates data into nodes based on class purity and is the precursor to the Random Forest model. Orange data mining, a unique application that can handle both discrete and continuous data, has an embedded tree widget that contains parameters such as Induce binary tree, min. number of instances in leaves, do not split subsets smaller than, and Limit the maximal tree depth⁽¹³⁾. The same model was utilized by⁽¹⁴⁾. where the decision tree model resulted to 88.9% accuracy in predicting on-time graduation of student.⁽¹⁵⁾ explains that decision trees are often favored for predictive modeling due to its accessibility and efficacy. The purpose of a decision tree is to divide a data set into smaller segments. Predictive modeling involves two phases. The initial phase involves constructing the tree through training, testing, and refining it with a pre-existing data set. In the subsequent phase, the tree is utilized to anticipate an outcome that is yet to be determined.

The model determines optimal splits using an impurity measure such as entropy. The entropy of a dataset is defined as:

$$H(S) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 p_i$$

where p_i represents the probability of class i . The algorithm selects features that maximize information gain, resulting in the most effective separation of classes. Decision trees were chosen due to their interpretability, efficiency, and suitability for small to medium-sized datasets. Additionally, they provide explicit decision rules that can be easily understood by educators and stakeholders.

2.5 Model Evaluation

To assess the performance of the predictive model, 10-fold cross-validation was employed. This method partitions the dataset into ten subsets, iteratively using nine subsets for training and one subset for testing, ensuring robust evaluation and minimizing bias. The following evaluation metrics were used:

Accuracy (CA): Measures the proportion of correctly classified instances

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

True positive (TP) refers to correctly predicted positive instances, true negative (TN) refers to correctly predicted negative instances, false positive (FP) refers to negative instances incorrectly classified as positive, and false negative (FN) refers to positive instances incorrectly classified as negative. Precision measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive cases out of all instances predicted as positive, while recall (sensitivity) refers to the model's ability to correctly identify actual positive cases. The F1-score represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced measure of a model's performance, particularly in cases of class imbalance. In addition, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Area Under the Curve (AUC) are used to evaluate the trade-off between the true positive rate and false positive rate across different classification thresholds.

These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of model performance beyond accuracy alone.

2.6 Tool for Predictive Modelling

The data preparation, predictive modeling, and model evaluation in this study were all carried out using the Orange Data Mining Software. Orange is a free and open-source machine learning and data visualization software. It offers a wide and diverse toolkit for creating visual data analysis workflows⁽¹⁶⁾.

2.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethics must always be followed when conducting research that deals with personal data from individuals. To ensure this, the names of the students were transformed into codes (stud1, stud2, stud3, stud4) prior to processing their grades in this study. Instead of numerical grades, only qualitative evaluations (o/vs/s/f/dne) and categorical data (Passed/Failed) were utilized. The objective of the researchers in conducting this study was to develop a model for forecasting student achievement in an introductory computing course through the use of educational data mining methods.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 The Model

The decision tree model was developed to predict student success in the Introduction to Computing course using specialized and applied coursework data from the Senior High School (SHS) TVL-ICT track. The results demonstrate that SHS academic performance can be effectively utilized to classify whether a student is likely to pass or fail in a foundational computing subject. Among the five input variables, specialized courses (SP1 and SP2) emerged as the most dominant predictors, indicating that students with stronger performance in these subjects are more likely to succeed. Applied courses (AP1–AP3) also contributed to the classification process, although their influence was comparatively lower, suggesting a supporting rather than primary role in shaping academic outcomes. These findings are consistent with prior studies emphasizing the importance of domain-specific knowledge in computing education. For instance,⁽¹⁷⁾ found that prior programming experience significantly influences student success in introductory computer science courses. Similarly,⁽¹⁸⁾ reported that students with stronger background knowledge in computing-related subjects tend to perform better due to enhanced problem-solving and logical reasoning skills. More recently,⁽¹⁹⁾ demonstrated that prior exposure to programming concepts improves academic performance and retention in computing programs. The present study aligns with these findings by showing that specialized ICT coursework, often focused on programming and systems development, serves as a strong predictor of academic success. However, the results also provide a more nuanced perspective compared to existing literature. While many studies treat prior academic performance as a generalized predictor (e.g., overall GPA), this study disaggregates SHS preparation into specialized and applied components. This distinction reveals that not all forms of prior learning contribute equally to success in computing education. In contrast to studies that highlight the broad importance of general academic skills, the findings suggest that applied subjects alone are insufficient predictors when compared to domain-specific coursework. This partially contradicts the notion that general academic preparedness uniformly translates to success across disciplines, instead reinforcing the discipline-specific nature of computing education.

Furthermore, the use of a decision tree classifier strengthens the validity of the findings when compared with traditional statistical approaches commonly used in prior studies. In⁽²⁰⁾ shows the growing importance of educational data mining techniques in uncovering hidden patterns in student data, while⁽²¹⁾ demonstrated that classification algorithms, including

decision trees, can achieve strong predictive performance in educational settings. Unlike regression-based models, which primarily capture linear relationships, decision trees provide interpretable, rule-based structures that reveal hierarchical interactions among variables. This methodological advantage enhances both the transparency and practical applicability of the model, particularly for institutional decision-making. The findings validate the effectiveness of the proposed predictive model while extending existing literature through a more granular and interpretable analysis of SHS coursework components. The consistency of the results with established studies, combined with the identification of differential predictor importance, supports the robustness of the model and reinforces its potential for early identification of at-risk students in computing education.

The decision tree model (Figure 2) was developed to predict student success in the Introduction to Computing course using both specialized and applied coursework data from the Senior High School (SHS) TVL-ICT track. The resulting model demonstrates that SHS academic performance can be effectively utilized to classify whether a student is likely to pass or fail in a foundational computing subject. Among the five input variables, the model identified both specialized and applied courses as contributing factors, although their levels of influence varied. The grades obtained in specialized courses (SP1 and SP2) emerged as the most dominant predictors in the classification process. Students who achieved higher performance levels in these subjects were consistently more likely to pass the Introduction to Computing course, suggesting that specialized ICT competencies, such as programming, are critical for academic success in computing-related programs. At the same time, applied courses (AP1-AP3) also contributed to the predictive structure of the model, albeit to a lesser extent, indicating that foundational and practical skills acquired during SHS still play a supporting role in student preparedness. The model structure highlights the combined influence of both types of coursework, reinforcing the importance of a holistic approach to SHS training. While specialized subjects provide depth in technical knowledge, applied subjects contribute to the development of general competencies that may indirectly support learning in higher education. These findings suggest that both components of the SHS curriculum are relevant, though their impact on predicting success in computing varies in magnitude.

Fig 2. Decision Tree Model

3.2 Model Evaluation

The predictive performance of the model was assessed using 10-fold cross-validation, resulting in an overall classification accuracy of 84.5% (Figure 3). This indicates that the model is effective in predicting student success in the Introduction to Computing course based on SHS coursework data. The relatively high accuracy supports the viability of using prior academic performance, particularly in specialized and applied subjects, as indicators of future academic outcomes.

Analysis of the confusion matrix (Figure 4) shows that the model was more effective in correctly identifying students who failed compared to those who passed, which is valuable in the context of early risk detection. However, some misclassifications were observed, particularly in predicting passing students, suggesting that additional factors beyond SHS coursework may also influence academic success in college. This highlights the inherent complexity of student performance and the limitations of relying solely on prior grades.

Evaluation results for target (None, show average over classes)					
Model	AUC	CA	F1	Precision	Recall
Tree	0.948	0.845	0.847	0.863	0.845

Fig 3. Model Classification Accuracy

		Predicted		Σ
		Failed	Passed	
Actual	Failed	19	2	21
	Passed	7	30	37
Σ		26	32	58

Fig 4. Confusion Matrix

Further evaluation using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) (Figure 5) curve indicates that the model performs better than random classification, with a satisfactory ability to distinguish between successful and at-risk students. The corresponding Area Under the Curve (AUC) value supports the reliability of the model across different classification thresholds. Overall, the evaluation results confirm that the model provides a reasonably accurate and robust prediction of student success using SHS academic data.

The results of this study have important implications for both curriculum development and academic support in education. First, the stronger predictive influence of specialized coursework suggests that these subjects play a crucial role in preparing students for computing-related programs in higher education. This underscores the need for educators and curriculum planners to ensure that specialized ICT subjects are effectively designed and aligned with college-level expectations. Second, while applied coursework showed a relatively lower predictive impact, its inclusion in the model indicates that it still contributes to student readiness. This suggests that applied subjects should not be overlooked, as they may support the development of essential skills such as problem-solving, adaptability, and practical application of knowledge, which are important in computing education. Third, the ability of the model to predict student success using SHS data provides an opportunity for early identification of at-risk students. Educational institutions can leverage similar predictive approaches to implement timely interventions, such as bridging programs or targeted academic support, to improve student outcomes in introductory computing courses. By utilizing both specialized and applied coursework data, institutions can gain a more comprehensive understanding of student preparedness and develop strategies that enhance the transition from secondary to tertiary education.

4 Conclusion

This study developed a predictive model to determine student success in an Introduction to Computing course using Senior High School (SHS) specialized and applied coursework data from Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Information and Communications Technology (TVL-ICT) graduates. The findings confirm that SHS academic preparation is a significant predictor of college-level performance, with the decision tree model achieving an accuracy of 84.5%. Specialized ICT subjects

Fig 5. ROC Curve

were identified as the most influential predictors, emphasizing the critical role of domain-specific competencies, while applied subjects provided complementary support in shaping overall student readiness. The primary novelty of this study lies in its granular and explainable modeling of SHS curriculum components as distinct predictors of academic success in computing education. The proposed model offers a scalable and data-driven decision-support tool for early identification of at-risk students. Educational institutions may integrate this approach into academic advising systems to enable timely and targeted interventions, such as bridging programs, curriculum adjustments, or personalized learning support. Furthermore, the results highlight the need for stronger vertical alignment between SHS ICT curricula and college-level computing requirements, particularly in reinforcing specialized competencies that directly impact academic success. Future research may extend this work by incorporating larger and multi-institutional datasets to improve generalizability, as well as by exploring ensemble and hybrid machine learning models to enhance predictive performance.

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